

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF CAPITAL BUDGETING

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Abstract: This article analyzes the practice of capital budgeting of joint-stock companies and the research results of foreign economists who conducted research in this direction. The methods used in the preparation of the capital budget of enterprises and their importance are considered. For enterprises, it is important to calculate the feasibility of an investment project using capital budgeting methods. Capital budgeting analysis is very useful in conducting research and analysis on feasibility of investment project planned by the enterprise.

Keywords: capital budgeting, net present value (NPV), discounting cash flow (DCF), accounting rate of return (ARR), internal rate of return (IRR).

The ongoing recession in the world economy is encouraging world investors to make investments in the economies of developing countries, which are growing twice or more compared to developed countries. Today, in the financial markets of developing countries, there is an increase in competition for capital, thereby increasing the urgency of the need to ensure a high return on investment funds and the task of effectively organizing capital budgeting for company managers.

At the same time, in today's fierce competition, long-term capital investment has become an important issue for joint-stock companies. Businesses are still trying to master proper capital budgeting techniques. Capital budgeting is one of the most important areas of financial management. There are several methods commonly used to evaluate capital budgeting projects in European countries, namely payback period, accounting rate of return, present value and internal rate of return, and profit index. In recent years, studies show that discounted cash flow (DCF), net present value (NPV), internal rate of return (IRR), payback period (PBP), rate of return (ARR), capital investment evaluation methods such as return on investment (ROI), real option valuation (ROV) are widely used. For the most part, equity community leaders and financial managers consider the internal rate of return (IRR) or non-discounted payment (PP) model to be more effective by scholars.

We believe that capital budgeting is a process used to evaluate a company's potential major projects or investments. Construction of a new factory, investment of company assets in foreign companies and approval or rejection by the management of the company is the main issue facing any business entity. As a part of capital budgeting, it can be understood that the company evaluates the cash inflows and outflows of prospective projects, evaluates whether the potential income it generates is suitable for the planned goals or not.

For some businesses, capital investment is important to create shareholder wealth. Today, it is very important to study the practices used in project evaluation. Internal rate of return (IRR) and net present value (NPV) have long been measures of corporate capital budgeting recognized by corporate governance and finance theorists, respectively. Although corporate management prefers the relevance of income-based capital budgeting methods such as IRR, some financial theorists based on economic theory favor the NPV method. Financial theorists have long identified the conditions under which certain methods of capital budgeting are superior to others. However, uncertainties in theoretical assumptions can significantly affect the consistency and superiority of the chosen capital budgeting method. Several foreign economists have conducted research in this direction, and there are different opinions in their approach.

Anne Farragher and Leung studied the capital investment management practices of large corporations in Malaysia, Singapore, and Hong Kong. According to him, companies in Malaysia, Singapore and Hong Kong use simple and complex methods for evaluating investment projects. Economists Baby and Sharma have studied various methods of capital budgeting in Indian industry. His research showed that more than 90 percent of companies used capital budgeting techniques. In addition, most businesses use the discounted cash flow (DCF) method for capital budgeting. At the same time, it was found that the internal rate of return (IRR) and payback period (PBP) methods are also used, which are popular methods of investment evaluation.

Block S believes that capital budgeting plays an important role in business management. Therefore, the managers of the joint-stock company should use complex analysis methods in this process and find knowledgeable specialists who have extensive experience in evaluating capital projects and know how to use relevant practices in making decisions. There are two important aspects of capital budgeting, namely organizational and management. From an organizational point of view, the enterprise should study sector relations based

on the size of financial assets and the capital budget decision. Large companies need to make sure they can make big and solid investments, while smaller companies need to make fewer and simpler ones. From a managerial point of view, a group of researchers argue that the problem of capital budgeting lies with the practitioner: the manager does not understand or know how to use the most appropriate methods, so he uses the simplest methods. From this point of view, it is necessary to check how the characteristics of the manager affect the creation of the capital budget of the enterprise.

For enterprises, it is important to calculate the feasibility of an investment project using capital budgeting methods. Capital budgeting analysis is very useful in conducting research and analysis on feasibility of investment project planned by the enterprise. In our opinion, capital budgeting is the evaluation of large projects and investments by companies, such as the construction of new production lines or the provision of new equipment and technologies to the enterprise, and the cash inflows and outflows of the project to determine whether the expected return from the process meets the established criteria. includes analysis.

Investment decisions are one of the tasks of the financial manager in the distribution of funds of joint-stock companies, investment is the investment in core or non-core assets for future profit. Before deciding whether to accept or reject an investment plan, financial managers must conduct an analysis to evaluate the investment. Investment in fixed assets is very important and necessary for companies providing goods or services. Fixed assets are the main capital in the establishment of a company. The main funds of the enterprise can be used for the production needs of the enterprise in order to increase the production activity of the enterprise. In enterprises that produce goods, the main assets are the equipment used in the daily production process. For service companies, fixed assets are those that support the production process. Other fixed assets owned by the enterprise may be in the form of buildings, vehicles and other auxiliary assets. Over time, fixed assets are damaged, they cannot be used optimally. This leads to the non-optimality of the production process and the disruption of the production process of the enterprise. Therefore, one of the important tasks facing enterprises is the implementation of large investment projects in order to manage cash flows, expand production, and modernize the enterprise technically and technologically.

Another important issue facing managers is that there are several potential risks involved in capital budgeting, including:

Market risk: changes in market conditions, changes in currency exchange rates or other economic factors can increase the capital budgeting losses of enterprises.

Mistakes in management: Mistakes in company management and government political mismanagement or corporate governance mistakes can lead to financial losses.

Investment Risk: Additional investments may be required during the capital budgeting process to generate mutual benefits, but not all of them may be compatible and/or out of date.

Decrease in demand: The goal of capital budgeting is to invest funds and increase profits, but involves the risk of a decrease in consumer demand or a decrease in income.

Political and legal risks: Political decisions, legal procedures and other political factors can affect the time of firm investment for companies.

Technology Risk: Automating a portion of capital budgeting or adopting new technologies involves technology risk for companies, such as technological tool failures or security issues. These risks are important to operators and are important to consider when determining deployment procedures and strategies.

Capital budgeting is an important process for businesses, but it is important to note that it has limitations. Being aware of these limitations allows us to make more informed decisions and improve the efficiency of our capital budgeting efforts. First, because capital budgeting depends on estimated cash flows, it is important to be careful when making estimates about the value and timing of cash flows.

Next, it is very important to get the discount rate right, because the wrong choice of the discount rate will jeopardize the efficiency of the whole project. Capital budgeting focuses on quantitative factors such as profitability and return on investment, which are important to consider when trying to determine how to spend limited capital! However, it is also important to consider qualitative factors such as brand reputation and employee morale.

Another important point is that in capital budgeting, non-cash expenses such as depreciation are not included in the capital budget. Taxes are also excluded. These costs should be considered separately, as they can significantly affect the overall financial results of the project. Once again, it is important to not only focus on cash flows, but also remember to use risk assessment and

sensitivity analysis to determine how (especially unexpected) changes in key variables may affect the financial sustainability of the project.

In conclusion, it can be said that the creation of the capital budget of the enterprise is a long-term investment decision-making process, which includes the allocation of financial resources of the joint-stock company for certain investment projects. This process includes the evaluation, selection and control of investment projects that are expected to bring financial benefits in the long term. Capital budgeting is an important part of a company's financial decisions because it involves the efficient use of funds and has a long-term impact on the enterprise. The primary goal of capital budgeting is to maximize enterprise value by selecting investment projects that generate positive cash flow and provide a level of return commensurate with the risks involved.

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